

Assessment of Health Communication Channels for Family Planning among Females of Reproductive Age Attending Sir Ganga Ram Hospital Lahore

Dr. Serena Taj

Roll No. 643-17

MPH

Supervised by

Almas Rasheed

MSC, MHA, MPH.

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University of Health Sciences Lahore

Institute Of Public Health Lahore

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1	Submission of Dissertation to the supervisor by student		<hr/> Dr. Serena Taj Student IPH, Lahore
2	Forwarded by supervisor to course coordinator IPH, Lahore		<hr/> Dr. Almas Rasheed IPH, Lahore
3	Forwarded by course coordinator to Dean IPH, Lahore		<hr/> Prof. Dr. Seema Imdad IPH Lahore
4	Forwarded by the Dean to the University of Health Sciences		<hr/> <i>Prof. Dr. Tajammal Mustafa</i> DEAN IPH Lahore
5	Examination		<hr/> Examiner

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It is hereby certified that the dissertation is based on the results of experiments carried out by Dr. Serena Taj and that it has not been previously presented for any postgraduate qualification. Dr. Serena Taj has done this research work under my supervision. She has fulfilled all the requirements and is qualified to submit the dissertation titled “Assessment of Health Communication Channels for Family Planning among Females of Reproductive Age Attending Sir Ganga Ram Hospital Lahore” for the award of the degree of MPH.

Almas Rasheed
MSC, MHA, MPH Australia.
Institute of Public Health, Lahore

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Word Form
CPR	Contraceptive Prevalence Rate
FGDs	Focused Group Discussions
FP	Family Planning
HCP	Healthcare Provider
IEC	Information, Education and Communication
IPC	Interpersonal Communication
KII	Key Informant Interview
LHWs	Lady Health Workers
mCPR	Modern Contraceptive Prevalence Rate
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
PTV	Pakistan Television
SGRH	Sir Ganga Ram Hospital
SPSS	Statistical Package for Social Sciences
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
USAID	United States Agency for International Development
WHO	World Health Organization
BTL	Billateral tubal ligation

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Abstract

Introduction

Implementation of Family Planning Programme in Pakistan remained challenging due to number of factors. In family planning, communication is a method to spread information regarding contraceptive means, change attitude of people towards voluntary decline of fertility, contraceptive use and norms about ideal family size. Both interpersonal communication and mass media are significant components of information, education and communication which are normally used to promote Family planning.

Objectives

The objectives of the study are to determine health communication channels for family planning; to determine most effective channel; and to identify the gaps in existing communication/message delivery to the population.

Material and Methods

It is descriptive cross-sectional study in which 88 women were included in quantitative part using systematic random sampling technique. In qualitative part purposive sampling technique was used, Four Focus group discussion were conducted, there were 6-8 women in each FGD. Whereas ten female health care providers of SGRH were interviewed in-depth. Data was collected through questionnaire, which was analyzed using SPSS 20.0. Frequencies and percentages were calculated and data was presented in tables and graphs. Confidentiality of the data was ensured and proper consent was obtained before data collection.

Results

Among 88 women, 65.9% were 26-35 years old, 50.0% studied up to matric, duration of marriage for 38.6% women was 11-15 years and 46.6% had 3-4 children. Among these women 98.9% had knowledge about family planning along with majority of FGD participants but 79.5% were using contraception, in FGDs participants this percentage showed a decline. 87.5% women availed family planning services in the past. 61.3% women suggested that they need to be informed about the side effects of contraceptive medicine. 92.0% women stated Mass media broadcast their preferable language and 97.5% said these messages are understandable for them. 74.7% got knowledge from television program but only (36.4%) and half of the FGDs said they can watch family planning programs on television while sitting with family. Health care providers and women believed that mass media alone cannot solve all their misconceptions. Therefore, preferred communication channel was a doctor 64.8% followed by LHW 50%, majority of FGD participants supported this view, but only 26.1% women stated that family planning personnel visited their homes, majority of the FGDs agreed to rare visit made by health personal. Greater percentage of women objected on the demonstration of Health workers regarding contraception methods without IEC material use. And 77.9% women were satisfied with the attitude of health care providers. 40.7% women had difficulty in communication with HCP. Spouse involvement in FP discussion with wife and health personal was only (8.1%). Health Care providers viewed that they need refresher course yearly.

Conclusion

The study concluded that family planning program of Pakistan is using different channels of communication which includes mass media, community events, interpersonal communication and digital media.

Study revealed television as one of the most effective channel of communication, however interpersonal communication was a favored mode of communication with greater outcomes and impacts.

Communication campaigns of the family planning program lack situational sensitivity and is failing to respond to the needs of targeted audience. There is lack of information and knowledge about the side effects of contraceptive methods in the population under study because of the capacity issues of health care providers.

Cultural and traditional barriers are still hindering family planning but these issues are not sufficiently addressed by communication strategies.

Keywords

Assessment, mass media, interpersonal communication, family planning, women

Introduction

The World population estimated to have reach 7.5 billion in April 2017.

United Nations estimates it will further increase to 11.2 billion by 2100.^[1]

Pakistan has one of the highest fertility rates among regions and lowest rate (35.0%) of contraceptive use in comparison to India 54%, Afghanistan 21%, China 85%, Japan 54%, Iran 82%, Bangladesh 62%, UK 84% and USA 62%, hampering socioeconomic development of masses due to an inverse relationship between economic indicators and fertility.^[2]

Pakistan's estimated population as of August 25, 2017 was 207.77 million people making it the world's fifth-most-populous country. There is annual average growth rate of 2.4% over a period of 1998-2017. As per the provisional results the urban population is slightly increased in Punjab as compared to other province.^[3]

Population growth has always been stressing environment in many ways like consumption of resources and waste production can eventually cause environmental catastrophe such as global warming. Scientist pondered; that Earth may accommodate the burden of trillion people but what would be the quality of life globally in future.^[4]

This is how Family Planning Programme took its birth and considered to be a tool for improving health, reducing poverty, and empowering individuals. The United States Agency for International Development (USAID) recognized the urgent need for family planning (FP) and important role of communication in this context therefore, began as early as 1970s to address communication issues, where health communication considered to be the means by which information about health is imparted and shared with other people.

Recent Studies conducted in Malawi and Bangladesh bear evidence regarding positive role of communication in influencing behavior change and contraception uptake by people. ^[5]

Family planning messages are conveyed through BCC Communication Programs. Behavior change communication comprises four main channels of communication: mass media, community-level events (often grouped under the heading of community mobilization), interpersonal communication/counseling, and electronic media. ^[6]

The term "population information, education and communication" (IEC) when used in context of family planning has broad meaning and series of specific goals, such as creating public awareness about the need of family planning, increase knowledge about its use, risks and where to obtain contraceptives, furthermore motivating couples and individuals to visit

family planning services, It is health workers ability for these forms of communication that distinguishes them from their audience, this can help in access to information with safe, affordable, effective and acceptable methods of contraception. With the appropriate knowledge and information about the new behavior and its relevance, women are able to make informed choices about their reproductive health.^[7]

Implementation of Family Planning Programme in Pakistan remains very challenging due to number of factors including historical & political strife and cultural restrictions on women constraining their empowerment. Along with lack of knowledge of where to obtain FP methods and lack of information on what women consider to be trusted sources of FP information and services, are key barriers that affect access to and utilization of FP methods in most of the countries.^[8]

World Health Organization (WHO) in its factsheet states, that 214 million women have high unmet demand for contraception. Countries need to do what works to improve contraceptive access, provision and choice for women and girls.^[9]

The media have been the subject of academic study for over 70 years. However, it is only in the last decade that media studies as a subject has really come into the public awareness.^[10]

In 70's the media messages delivered on Pakistan Television (PTV) and Radio Pakistan publicized the availability of family planning services. Promotions of small family norm were indirectly presented by educational and motivational messages. For example, radio messages were usually "spot" announcements about the availability of contraceptives through various channels or jingles such as "Fewer children means happy families". Most media messages were telecasted every next week. Multiple exposure through the media play important role in educating couple on the benefits of small families and provide regular information on availability of contraception services and the various methods for contraception and its use. Study shows that exposure to the media advertising is known to help to change attitudes and behavior of a targeted population.^[11]

Era of Muhammad Zia-ul-Haq 1988 was considered to be the end of media liberalization. In late 90s national television telecasted condom ads but with certain limitations until mid-2000s. In 2000 Pervez Musharraf supported free media and this promoted health communication on television regarding sensitive issues such as family planning, sexual and reproductive health. Data from the Pakistan Demographic and Health Surveys show that 44% of 5184 women in 2006-07 were exposed to family planning messages on radio and television, compared with 21% of 8041 in 1990-91. Revised

policies have allowed family planning commercials but with certain limitations.^[12]

Government of Pakistan took important steps in 1953 regarding establishment of Family Planning Programme in Pakistan and initiated its programme now called Rahnuma earlier known as Family Planning Association of Pakistan, The Population Welfare Programme and the National Family Planning Council (eventually the Population Welfare Division of the Health Ministry) were also initiated in this decade. Interest in FP revived in the 1990s.

Lady Health Workers' (LHW) program was started by the Pakistan Ministry of Health in 1994. Government spent \$155 million during the first eight years of the programme, in which 11% was external donation. It contributed to the rapid rise in CPR (contraceptive prevalence rate) in rural areas, emphasized on maternal and child health and also delivered family planning services. The programme set out to select, train and deploy 100,000 female community health workers, known as 'Lady Health Workers', throughout the country by 2005. These women provided door to door health and family planning services, supplied with oral and injectable contraceptives and condoms to distribute to their communities. The LHW programme joined hands with NGO (non-governmental organization) sector. Inauguration of Green Star and Key Social Marketing NGOs promoted first level care

facilities to the community thus improving the delivery of primary health care service [13]

Similarly, DKT international a charitable non-profit organization promotes family planning and HIV prevention through social marketing was founded in 1989 has its important role in promoting family planning in Pakistan as well. [14]

Present study regarding “Assessment of health communication channels for family planning among women of reproductive age” is carried out at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital Lahore to see the effectiveness of these channels and their output in framing future policies.

Literature Review

Family planning

Family planning helps couples to have their desired number of offspring and to determine spacing between pregnancies. This is only possible through infertility treatment or contraceptive methods utilization. ^[9]

The Lady Health Worker Program and National Program for FP was initiated with the main objectives such as to decrease poverty through offering fundamental primary health care services and enhancing maternal, infant and child health and offering family planning services. Each lady health worker's catchment area includes almost a population of 1000 individuals or 150 houses. The LHWs provide counseling on numerous health problems, offer family planning services, refer patients for antenatal care, immunize children, provide necessary medical care, and encourage community mobilization. ^[15]

Contraceptive use

In several areas of the worlds, the use of contraception has been increased, particularly in Latin America and Asia but it is still less in sub-Saharan Africa. Modern contraceptive usage has increased slightly from 54 percent during 1990 to 57.4 percent during 2015. Regionally, the percentage of women 15-49 years old reporting utilization of modern method of contraception has increased very little or plateau between the years 2008 and 2015. It went in African from 23.6 – 28.5 percent while in Asia raised slightly from 60.9 – 61.8 percent and remained constant at 66.7 percent in Caribbean and Latin America. Contraceptive use by males makes up comparatively minute subset of above incidence rates. The methods of modern contraception for males are restricted to male sterilization (vasectomy) and condoms. [9]

The overall prevalence rate of contraception in Pakistan on the basis of mCPR (modern contraceptive prevalence rate) by assessing users of each method, during 2015 to 2016 has been calculated as 35.5 percent. In Regional / Provincial setup, the mCPR for province Punjab is 38.9 percent, for Sindh 25.0 percent, for Khyber Pakhtunkhwa 46.0 percent, for Baluchistan 13.8 percent, for Federal district Islamabad 81.8 percent, for AJK 17.6 percent, for FATA 10 percent and for Gilgit-Baltistan the mCPR is

22 percent during 2015-16. In addition, the overall mCPR for 2014-15 has been calculated as 32.7 percent. Thus, mCPR in the years 2015-16 has raised by 8.6 percent, when compared with previous years. [2]

Global unmet need for contraception

Among developing countries, 214 million women of childbearing age who desire to prevent pregnancy are not using modern method of contraception. For contraception, unmet need remain very high due to lack of FP services. In Africa, 24.2 percent women of childbearing age have unmet need of modern contraceptive methods. In Latin America, Caribbean and Asia, areas with comparatively high prevalence of contraception – the unmet need levels are 10.2 percent and 10.7 percent, respectively. [9]

Communication in family planning

In the context of family planning, communication is a means used to spread information regarding contraceptive methods, to change attitude of people towards voluntary decline of fertility, contraceptive use and promote small family size. Communication enables societies to follow novel ideas for adopting healthy behavior. Such communication can take place both impulsively, between and within social groups of community and intentionally, by means of designed intervention of NGOs, government and commercial enterprises. This designed communication can start change, quicken changes already in progress or strengthen change which has

already happened. Planned communication targeted at decision and policy makers, named advocacy has capability to cause change and increase resource allocation and support for people and reproductive health care programs at all stages. Communicating regarding family planning and reproductive behavior is a challenging job. It deals with extremely personal life aspects wherein cultural and social obstacles exist that restrain open discussion that is mostly tricky not just between couples but also between clients and health care provider. So as to encourage small family model and to bring behavioral and attitudinal change, communication campaigns have been initiated to attain objective within established socio-cultural environment of country. [16]

Strategies applied for the communication of family planning

For the promotion of family planning several campaigns have been employed since 1960s, making it a health subject with longest communication campaign history in electronic communication era. There is yet a great requirement for the campaigns of family planning and more generally the reproductive health, such programs play a significant role in protecting women and infants' lives, assist couples to achieve desired size of family and to expand opportunities for women in their families and communities. In addition, FP programs are significantly addressing young adults and men requirements. In spite of availability of FP methods, researches demonstrate that contraceptive use is not common because

millions of women who desire to delay next pregnancy or don't want to have more children are not utilizing any kind of method. Family planning unmet need exist in all areas of developing world.

Communication campaigns are able to initiate, speed up or maintain FP behavior change because such campaigns can educate individuals regarding their choices, update them about supply sources, introduce novel values and address misconceptions. [17]

Both interpersonal communication and mass media are significant components of Information Education and communication program (IEC) which are normally used to encourage FP program. The mass media use movies, TV, radio, billboards and posters etc. whereas interpersonal communication employs individual qualification and counseling, home visits and group meetings, etc. for the promotion of family planning. [18]

Mass media and family planning

Mass media is most useful tool to provide accurate and enough information regarding use of contraception. The idea regarding use of contraception mostly faces resistance; in developing states the fear regarding elevated infant death rates, religion reasons regarding family planning, doubt of motives of FP campaigns sponsors, inadequate knowledge of people and unfavorable rumors regarding contraception usage effects its use. [19]

When mass media is used adequately it plays an imperative role in the promotion of use of contraception especially among developing states in which they are seen appealing due to their extensive coverage and probable cost effectiveness. The mass media makes individual careful about use of contraception and gives them a chance to assess the knowledge and services provided and to test the techniques as suggested. It leads to contraceptive adoption. [19]

Mass media has specific advantages and attributes that provide them special capability to support mass media communication involving the education and information. Mass media works like a diffusion channel contributing to enhanced contraceptive use. Mass media can feature explicit FP messages which persuade both information and liking about contraception. Secondly, mass media can operate through exposing viewers to numerous lifestyles which value small size of family. [19]

As per UNESCO (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization), strategies for utilizing mass media for the encouragement of contraceptive use must have radio, television, press, audio visual units and print media. The TV should have commercials; documentaries / drama; programs for women, features and magazine programs. Radio must have serials, plays, programs for women, songs, jingles and magazine programs. The print media and press must have commercials, features, cartoon strips,

literature, leaflets, posters and pamphlets. The film also have advertisements, documentaries, newsreels and cartoons. ^[19]

The influence of mass media regarding utilization of contraception refers to methods wherein mass media affects that how audiences behave and think with regards to contraceptive use. UNESCO indicates that mass media not only have press, films, radio and television but also have local song, dance, story tellers, puppet shows and several other communication means at local level. ^[19]

When mass media used adequately can offer a change not just in the attitudes but also in the behavior and it can be used to inform and educate individuals about the availability and use of contraceptive services.

Knowledge which is acquired could modify people desires and attitudes and can speed up contraception adaptation causing a change in the behavior. The media campaign which is well-designed can influence the people behavior and play considerable role in creating helpful social environment favorable for behavioral change. Hence, media campaigns can encourage novel ideas which in turn can encourage or lead to individuals to act in new manners and to accept contraceptive usage. ^[19]

Interpersonal communication and family planning

Communication activities are the basic in almost each FP program. They are utilized to support idea of FP programs in addition to particular methods of contraception that are accessible and locate places where these products and services are available. To disseminate message regarding use of contraception, several communication channels are used like mass media and interpersonal communication. [7]

Posters and interpersonal Communication (IPC) that carry instructive messages are forms which are very helpful in transmitting knowledge and messages regarding FP methods in the small villages and towns where much advanced communication is not available. Hence, making interpersonal communication an important component to transmit messages about reproductive health among women. [7]

Also, interpersonal communication is used by involving '*stratified users*' who are provided with stuff to distribute among their fellows and community members. For example: a successful family model can be utilized to convey messages to the peers. [7]

Literature demonstrates that interpersonal communication has long been recognized as a useful method to change behavior. It is believed that individuals are more likely to modify their behavior once persuaded to do so by the other people they know. Therefore, when people talk regarding mass media campaigns with others about reproductive health, response they get,

is significant for the decision making to use or not use family planning. Hence, IPC is important in strengthening the positive effects of media messages.^[7]

Studies further revealed that the mass media could be a helpful tool to motivate individuals to use family planning. Although, it is discussed that, following a revelation to the mass media messages regarding family planning, interpersonal communication discussion regarding such messages was a significant intermediate level in the procedure of deciding to utilize or to not utilize contraception. Interpersonal communication was to boost the exposure effects to mass media messages regarding behavior of contraceptive usage. Findings highlighted that those women who had exposure to mass media and discussed media messages with other individuals, were more possible to utilize contraceptives when compared with those who did not discuss such messages.^[20]

Spousal communication is one of the examples of interpersonal communication that is closely related to family planning usage after revelation to the communication. There are assumptions that communication cause FP usage and vice versa. Significance of spousal communication is mostly emphasized during research and FP programs and it is observed by analysts as first stage in rational fertility decision-

making process. Studies indicated that communication amount that occurs between the spouses is positively related to use of contraception. [21]

It further demonstrated that communication lack regarding family planning, could be linked with the misconceptions regarding views of spouse about family planning that, in turn, could restrain decision making. The behavior change interventions like IPC that intended to encourage family planning, motivated psychosocial factors related to spousal communication, hence, causing family planning usage. [21]

While the media campaigns made efforts to modify behavior patterns, they may not generally cause FP adoption. Spousal communication effects on the family planning usage were intervened by each spouse relative power in the process of decision making. It was associated with the study done in India which indicated that husbands were main decision makers and discussion initiators regarding family planning usage. [21]

Hence, spousal communication was most significant factor in family planning adoption because it started behavioral factors change such as knowledge and attitudes and motivation towards the family planning that in turn encourages family planning usage. It was inspired by both IPC and media communication. [7]

Studies revealed that FP programs were utilized to decline birth rate to stabilize population, at a level constant with need of national economy through generating worldwide knowledge regarding FP method utilization. However, even with great awareness regarding FP methods, there existed a broad gap between the knowledge and FP methods acceptance. [7]

Assessment of health communication channels for Family planning among women

Sultan and Younus (2010) undertook a study to assess the effectiveness of television as a tool in altering different levels of human behavior from increasing awareness, persuasion, decision making and confirmation of decision about family planning messages. The study involved 150 married couples of reproductive age of Peshawar. Study revealed that 80% respondents had a knowledge ranging from “to some extent” (36%), “to great extent” (29%) and “completely” (15%). Only 13% were unaware of the issue. Similarly, 14% respondents stated that television changed their attitude towards family planning “completely”. Another 18% were of the opinion that it changed their attitude “to great extent” and 38% marked as “to some extent”. Only 23% denied any role of television in attitude formation. As per analysis, 13% of the respondents consider television as a potential source for decision making for family planning. Only 11% respondent used television “completely” for confirmation of their decision regarding family planning. Study concluded that television played a

significant role at the knowledge and persuasion level however it was found as less effective at decision and confirmation stages. [22]

Kabir and Amirul Islam (2000) carried out a study among 871 newly married urban Bangladeshi women to assess the impact of mass media family planning programs on current contraceptive use. The analysis suggested that radio played a significant role in spreading family planning messages among eligible clients; 38% of women with access to a radio had heard of family planning messages while the figures for TV and newspaper were 18.5% and 8.5% respectively. Education, number of living children and current contraceptive use were important predictors of exposure to any mass media family planning messages. [23]

A study was done by Rehema (2013) to find out the role of interpersonal communication in the use of family planning among women in Nairobi. During study 36 women of reproductive age between 15-45 years participated. The results of study indicated that various communication channels such as broadcast media, print media and interpersonal communication were used in behavior change campaigns. However, various interpersonal communication channels were found to be the most effective method used by women in passing messages of family planning. Although other communication channels were commercial and advertorial unlike interpersonal communication which was more informative and educative as it employed dialogue among women. Study recommended

that for adequate use of family planning methods various stakeholders like government, media and development partners should engage in effective communication on reproductive health. [7]

Ajaero and coworkers (2016) conducted a study to investigate the relationship between access to mass media messages and use of family planning in Nigeria. Results showed that access to television and radio messages increase the likelihood of the use of family planning. Also people with higher socioeconomic status used more family planning methods. There is need to improve the socioeconomic status of the populations. Also, the quality and regularity of mass media messages should be improved. [24]

Tsehay and Coworkers (2017) studied the impact of mass media exposure on family planning. They conducted Surveys in 2000, 2005 and 2011 on 28161 individuals in Ethiopia and found in 2011, 5% women reported seeing family planning messages in newspaper, community events accounted 37.3% being the most common source. Radio was the second most common with a percentage of 30.3 and only 14% women reported seeing a family planning message on television. Mass media acknowledge to be a positive source of family planning message. [25]

A similar study was conducted by Jacob J on West African adolescents. He interviewed 17087 women in Burkina Faso and 15688 in Senegal. In Burkina Faso higher proportion of women reported being exposed to radio

than TV or print media, whereas in Senegal similar proportion reported radio and TV as the source of family planning message. He suggested mobile phone to be the most appropriate mode of communication between women and health care providers as suggested by women as this technology is most commonly being use this way in Kenya. Variables such as interaction with health care providers was not discussed. The study suggested additional research on the topic to provide newer technologies in context of family planning communication. [26]

Raut MK in (2011) conducted research on the effect of Interpersonal communication and mass media on contraception use in Bangladesh. He gathered data of Bangladesh demographic and health survey from 1999 to 2011 and compared both variables. In his findings only 14.5% women heard about the family planning message from health worker 24.84% reported Television 2.88% radio and 3.05% from newspaper. He further stated that 76.85% were contraception users who received information from health workers, it clearly indicated that Interpersonal communication accounted to be the most effective tool in Bangladesh in initiating behavior change. Study recommended to facilitate interpersonal communication sector by funding communication through field workers, outreach workers and counselors. [27]

Frigters EM used mix methodology in (2013) to study the role of mobile phone in increasing contraceptive use in rural Uganda. Barriers in

contraception use regarding this method include lack of access, ownership and interpersonal communication .Contraception message was delivered through SMS, there were 40 local languages in Uganda, some people were unable to read message while language and literary issues accounted as barriers. Many couples use common mobile phone and contraception messages thus delivered can cause serious problems as many ladies use family planning methods without the consent of husband Choice of preference of communication channel is as follows first health education, second mobile phone, third radio, fourth television last choice was poster or leaflets; interpersonal and radio were considered to be number one choice.

[28]

In this study Sharjabad and coworkers conducted research on barriers of modern contraceptive practices among Asian women by using 6 data basis for literature search during 2002-2012.Lack of family planning knowledge was one of the chief indicators leading to low CPR. Research among Asian women revealed limitation in women access to contraception and abortion services and that they were not comfortable requesting EC pill from health provider of same ethnicity. Related to health care centers in Pakistan among the unsatisfactory variables was the non-availability of contraception, cost, long waiting hours, shortage of women staff, etc. Researcher highlighted that family planning programme, reforming the health system and reproductive health education through mass media are

important indicators to create awareness of contraception use among Asian women. [29]

Malik ZI and his colleagues studied knowledge, attitude and practice of contraception among women attending Sheikh Zaid Hospital Rahim Yar Khan from Jan 2011 to June 2011. On sample size of 500 married women. Among them sources of family planning are as follows: 28.40% reported knowledge gained from Health professional, 32% relative, 9.4% TV and 2.4% Parents. Malik advised to improve the educational status of women to facilitate them towards family planning education. [30]

Another study was conducted by Netey and coworkers regarding Awareness, Perceptions and practice of family planning among community members living in Kintampo District of Ghana in (2011). It was a mixed research based on six Focused Group Discussions (FGDs) among men and women aged 15 - 49 years, discussion groups comprised of 8 - 12 persons; men and women were separately placed in three age-groups (15 - 25, 26 - 36, 37 - 49 years), out of a potential 7839 respondents contacted, 7171 made up of 4956 women and 2225 males, completed the survey interviews successfully. When asked about family planning education sources, the most common source of family planning method was radio 50.4%, television 28.2% social events 29.2%; 7.9% were magazines. Public health sector dominated the source of family planning methods therefore researcher

advised to strengthen the family planning health care system by ensuring adequate staff strength. [31]

Islam S and H Mahedi studied women knowledge, attitude, approval of family planning and contraceptive use in Bangladesh. In Jan 2014 he conducted survey and data was collected through face to face interview. At first stage, ten Mahallas (cluster) were randomly selected from 33 Mahallas (total cluster). At the second, stage 430 married women were selected randomly from the ten Mahallas. Study revealed that proper knowledge of women is directly related to contraceptive use in society which in turn is related to the efforts of Bangladesh government and NGO initiated family planning programmes. Study concluded that government should give target based family planning approach to increase knowledge on contraception. Mostly study was based on women education and type of contraception adopted. [32]

Khan MM, Shaikh ST and coworkers on a sample of 102 surveyed house in (2014) collected data regarding knowledge and practice of contraception. In Urban slum Community of Mumbai. Out of Sample 67 respondents were users and 35 were non user, where 82.35% of population commented health workers to be the source of family planning information while 75.49% commented media, doctor were commented to be the least important source only 46.07%. Researcher acknowledge the role of National family

planning programme and health care provider in educating masses but emphasized on male contraception education separate health education session for males because without proper male counseling contraception cannot be practiced.^[33]

Research on role of health promotion applications regarding contraception was done in March (2015) by Lunde B and Coworkers, they generated a complete list of IOS apps relevant to contraception by searching Apple iTunes store. Apps providing general information to the community regarding contraception included ask UK, birth control, contraception, a guide to option sets. This study did not involve survey population regarding their views about these apps, some of the apps like g power, plan a birth control and my choice allowed users to enter health information and select desired characteristics of method. Researcher recommended health educators and providers to improve the apps data by uploading accurate information and periodically upgrading it. ^[34]

A cross sectional survey conducted in (2014) by USAID funded program Tappis H and coworkers collected the survey data, multistage sampling procedure was used to select 6200 women of reproductive age. Source of contraception, information was among variables, women responded that major source of family planning education was watching television i.e. 43.0%,39.3% had received information from a doctor,35.2% from relatives

and 18.7 from mother in law. It was a different study conducted on contraception behavior of women in postpartum period and their views in that period, this study implies that women should be counseled at such timings when they can psychologically accept behavior change habits such as postpartum period. [35]

Odewale and teammates (2016) performed a study to examine several exposures to the information regarding contraceptive use and family planning among women in Nigeria. Study revealed that exposure to FP information through newspaper, TV, radio and health care facility were significantly associated with increased use of contraception in Nigeria. Also, use of contraception was significantly associated with women characteristic for example age, residence, education, marital status, religion, work status and wealth index. Results showed that married women who heard about family planning at health care facility were using 1.5 times when compared with those who did not hear, to report using contraception, and those women who exposed to numerous channels of FP information were using 2.5 times when compared with those who were unexposed to contraceptive methods usage. Hence the policies that support more qualified healthcare workers should be made to encourage women for the utilization of contraception. [36]

A study was undertaken by Adekunle and fellows (2004) to assess the role of mass media, TV and radio in FP messages. During study 503 women of childbearing age residing in Nigeria participated. Results showed that radio was most frequent information source. Among women, 53% reported that radio was the major source of information regarding FP messages, 10.1% said television despite of the fact that 68.5 percent women had television ownership while 89.1 percent had radio. Similarly 72% women said they never visited clinic for family planning services. For women, the most preferred television program was drama while for radio, the news was more preferred. Study concluded family planning messages should be intensified and integrated in radio news and television drama as these programs could play an important role in the use of family planning methods. ^[37]

Rationale of the study

Various means of communication are used by family planning program in Pakistan have been studied. However effectiveness in various means have not been fully explored. Rising level of population growth and existence of Unmet need for contraception indicates that communication strategy adopted by the family planning programme needs improvement, therefore this study is undertaken to assess the health communication channels of family planning.

Objectives

The objectives of the study are:

- To determine health communication channels for family planning.
- To determine most effective channel for family planning.
- To identify the gaps in existing communication/message delivery to the population.

Material and Methods

Study Design

It is a descriptive cross-sectional study of mixed methodology.

Study Setting

The study was conducted at Ganga Ram Hospital Lahore.

Study Population

The study population was women of Reproductive age (15-49 years).

Study Duration

The duration of study was three month.

Sample Size

From the reference study [2] where CPR of April, 2017 is 35.5 the sample size calculated is 88 women for quantitative part of study.

The screenshot shows a software window titled "Perform Estimation" with a dropdown menu set to "1.1. Estimating a population proportion with specified absolute precision". The window is divided into two sections: "Please select the desired unknown:" and "Please enter the remaining values:". In the first section, "Sample size" is selected with a radio button. In the second section, the following values are entered: "1 - α" is 95, "P" is 0.35, "d" is 0.10, and "n" is 88. At the bottom, the formula
$$n = \frac{z_{1-\alpha/2}^2 P(1-P)}{d^2}$$
 is displayed. There are buttons for "Print", "Help", and "Close" in the bottom right corner.

In qualitative part four focus group discussion were conducted, there were 6-8 members in each FGD, whereas 10 female health care providers of SGRH were interviewed in-depth.

Sampling Technique

Systematic Random Sampling technique was used for Quantitative part and Purposive sampling technique was used for Qualitative part of study.

Sample Selection

Inclusion Criteria

- Married women of reproductive age attending Sir Ganga Ram Hospital.

Exclusion criteria

- Infertile

Methodology

Data Collection Procedure

It is a descriptive cross sectional study of mixed methodology (Quantitative and Qualitative). In Quantitative part systematic random sampling technique was used in which every 5th women was selected for a sample of 88 women attending and admitted in Ob/Gyn OPD, wards and family planning welfare center of Sir Ganga Ram Hospital. Questionnaire was pretested by a pilot study on 20 women who were not part of study sample.

The first part of survey questionnaire based on respondent bio-data and the second part dealt with the core issues of topic. Quantitative data was collected by personally interviewing and filling research questionnaire by the researcher. In Qualitative part Purposive sampling technique was used. Focus group discussions were conducted with women of reproductive age and ten female health care providers of SGRH were interviewed in-depth. There are 15 Family Welfare Center working under SGRH in different areas of Lahore. Each interview lasted for 10-15 minute, one-on-one sessions offered participants the chance to speak more freely and offered the interviewer the opportunity to probe about barriers and effectiveness of health communication channels regarding family planning.

To fully assess the communication barriers providers and clients were included in qualitative part of study.

FGDs were conducted at SGRH. Four FGDs were conducted there were 6-8 members in each FGD, the interview guide was drafted in English and then translated into Urdu, interview guide was pretested on one group. Interviews were conducted in local languages Urdu and Punjabi by the researcher and supervisor and were audio recorded, then translated and transcribed into English by the researcher.

Data Analysis

It was mixed methodology study (qualitative and quantitative) therefore two sets of data was obtained. The survey was conducted and qualitative data was collected based on findings of survey. Interviews were translated and transcribed into English. Quantitative Data was coded, the thematic coding framework was then applied to assess all interview transcripts. The analysis looked for patterns and associations focusing on the drivers and barriers to health communication channels for family planning, data was analyzed using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) version 20.0. Frequency and percentage tables were generated for all possible variables related to categorical data. Bar and pie diagrams were used in the same context.

Ethical Consideration

Informed verbal consent was taken prior to the interview from the respondents. The confidentiality of the information was ensured and maintained as per Helsinki Protocol. Approval from Ethical Review Committee IPH and concerned authorities of Sir Ganga Ram Hospital Lahore was obtained.

Outcome and Utilization

Pakistan demography reveals multicultural and multiethnic society scattered in urban and rural areas having different levels of education and psychological approach. In BCC regarding family planning, different methodology of health communication channels need to be adopted for each sector having different values, culture and different locations because different locations have different problems. The expected result of this research will reveal communication gaps and barriers therefore; by undertaking possible measures for betterment of communication system we can facilitate women of Pakistan to adopt family planning methods. Furthermore, it will guide the policy makers to oversee the fact, why population of Pakistan is increasing dramatically despite spending huge budget on family planning sector each year, thus by formulating better strategies for communication and promoting family planning population growth and the resulting negative impacts on the economy, environment, and national and regional development can be minimized in future.

Estimated Cost of the Project and Item Used

Sr.No.	Name of Item	Quantity	Cost(in Rupees)
1.	Paper 80 grams	04 rims	2000
2.	Photocopy	600 pages	1400
3.	Transportation (self)	Multiple	15000
4.	Communication	Multiple	1000
5.	Assistant	1x10 weeks	10000
6.	Book binding	5 copies	5000
Total			34400

Plan of Work

(Maximum time period for work in weeks)

Weeks	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	14	16
Preparing research protocol														
Preparing questionnaire														
Data/sample collection														
Data analysis														
Compiling and writing														

Findings of Quantitative Analysis

Table – 1

Frequency distribution of women according to socio-demographic characteristics

$n = 88$

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age		
≤25 years	23	26.1
26-35 years	58	65.9
>35 years	7	8.0
Total	88	100.0
Mean ± SD	29.18 ± 5.32	
Education		
Illiterate	8	9.1
Madrasa	10	11.4
Matric	44	50.0
Above matric	26	29.5
Total	88	100.0
Duration of marriage		
Less than 5 years	15	17.0
5-10 years	31	35.2
11-15 years	34	38.6
16-20 years	7	8.0
More than 20 years	1	1.2
Total	88	100.0

Table-1 exhibits that among 88 women, 23 (26.1%) were upto 25 years old and 58 (65.9%) were 26-35 years old while only 7 (8.0%) women were more than 35 years old. The mean age of the women was 29.18 ± 5.32 years.

Among these women, 8 (9.1%) were illiterate, 10 (11.45) had Madrassa education, 44 (50.0%) studied upto matric and 26 (29.5%) women were above matric.

Result shows that duration of marriage for 15 (17.0%) women was less than 5 years, for 31 (35.2%) duration was 5-10 years, for 34 (38.6%) was 11-15 years and for 7 (8.0%) women duration was 16-20 years while for only 1 (1.2%) women the marriage duration was more than 20 years.

Figure – 1

Frequency Distribution of Women according to age

Table – 2

**Frequency distribution of women according to number of
children**

n = 88

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Total number of children		
1-2	30	34.1
3-4	41	46.6
>4	17	19.3
Total	88	100.0
Mean \pm SD	3.40 \pm 1.59	
Number of male children		
0	4	4.5
1-2	71	80.7
3-4	10	11.4
>4	3	3.4
Total	88	100.0
Number of women children		
0	11	12.5
1-2	55	62.5
3-4	20	22.7
>4	2	2.3
Total	88	100.0

Table-2 indicates that among 88 women, 30 (34.1%) had 1-2 children and majority 41 (46.6%) had 3-4 children while 17 (19.3%) women had more than 4 children. The mean number of children was 3.40 ± 1.59 .

Among the women, only 4 (4.5%) had no male child, majority 71 (80.7%) had 1-2 male children, 10 (11.4%) women had 3-4 male children and 3 (3.4%) women had more than 4 male children.

Likewise among 88 women, 11 (12.5%) had no women child, 55 (62.5%) had 1-2 women children, 20 (22.7%) women had 3-4 women children and 2 (2.3%) women had more than 4 women children.

Table – 3

**Frequency distribution of women according to
contraceptive use**

n = 88

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Use of contraception		
Yes	70	79.5
No	18	20.5
Total	88	100.0
Methods of contraception		
Copper T	<i>n</i> = 70	
Yes	8	11.4
No	62	88.6
Total	70	100.0
Injection	<i>n</i> = 70	
Yes	12	17.1
No	58	82.9
Total	70	100.0
Tubal ligation	<i>n</i> = 70	
Yes	10	14.3
No	60	85.7
Total	70	100.0

Implant	<i>n</i> = 70	
Yes	16	22.9
No	54	77.1
Total	70	100.0
Condom	<i>n</i> = 70	
Yes	30	42.9
No	40	57.1
Total	70	100.0
Tablets	<i>n</i> = 70	
Yes	17	24.3
No	53	75.7
Total	70	100.0
Natural methods	<i>n</i> = 70	
Yes	19	27.1
No	51	72.9
Total	70	100.0

Table-3 describes that among 88 women, 70 (79.5%) were using contraception while 18 (20.5%) were not using contraception.

Among women who were using contraception, 8 (11.4%) were using Copper-T, 12 (17.1%) injections, 10 (14.3%) tubal ligation, 16 (22.9%) implant, 30 (42.9%) condom, 17 (24.3%) tablets and 19 (27.1%) women were using natural methods.

Table – 4

Frequency distribution of women according to media ownership

n = 88

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Media ownership		
Yes	83	94.3
No	5	5.7
Total	88	100.0
Types of media		
Radio	<i>n</i> = 83	
Yes	20	24.1
No	63	75.9
Total	83	100.0
Television	<i>n</i> = 83	
Yes	79	95.2
No	4	4.8
Total	83	100.0
Newspaper	<i>n</i> = 83	
Yes	22	26.5
No	61	73.5
Total	83	100.0

Table-4 depicts that among 88 women, 83 (94.3%) had media ownership and only 5 (5.7%) women had no media ownership.

Among women who had media ownership, 20 (24.1%) had radio, majority 79(95.2%) had television and 22 (26.5%) women had newspaper.

Table – 5

**Frequency distribution of women according to knowledge
about family planning**

n = 88

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Knowledge about family planning		
Yes	87	98.9
No	1	1.1
Total	88	100.0
Source of knowledge		
Radio program	<i>n</i> = 87	
Yes	5	5.7
No	82	94.3
Total	87	100.0
TV program	<i>n</i> = 87	
Yes	65	74.7
No	22	25.3
Total	87	100.0
Newspaper	<i>n</i> = 87	
Yes	7	8.1
No	80	91.9
Total	87	100.0

Doctor	<i>n</i> = 87	
Yes	33	37.9
No	54	62.1
Total	87	100.0
LHV/LHW	<i>n</i> = 87	
Yes	58	66.7
No	29	33.3
Total	87	100.0
Relative	<i>n</i> = 87	
Yes	45	51.7
No	42	48.3
Total	87	100.0
Mobile phone	<i>n</i> = 87	
Yes	4	4.6
No	83	95.4
Total	87	100.0

Table-5 reveals that among 88 women, 87 (98.9%) had knowledge about family planning while only 1 (1.1%) women had no such knowledge.

Among women who had knowledge about family planning, 5 (5.7%) got knowledge from radio program, 65 (74.7%) from television program, 7 (8.1%) from newspaper, 33 (37.9%) from doctors, 58 (66.7%) from LHV/LHWs, 45(51.7%) general idea from discussion with relatives and 4 (4.6%) women got knowledge from mobile phones.

Table – 6

**Frequency distribution of women according to preferred
communication channel**

n = 88

	Yes	No
Television	40 (45.5%)	48 (54.5%)
Doctor	57 (64.8%)	31 (35.2%)
LHV/LHW	44 (50.0%)	44 (50.0%)
Newspaper	6 (6.8%)	82 (93.2%)
Mobile phone	10 (11.4%)	78 (88.6%)
Relative	7 (8.0%)	81 (92.0%)

During interview clients preferred more than one communication channel. -
Above table asserts that television was preferred communication for 40(45.5%) women, doctor for 57 (64.8%) women, LHV/LHWs for 44(50.0%) women, newspaper for 6 (6.8%) women, mobile phones for 10 (11.4%) women and relatives for 7 (8.0%) women.

Table – 7

**Frequency distribution of women according to perception
about mass media**

n = 88

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Mass media uses preferable language		
Yes	81	92.0
No	7	8.0
Total	88	100.0
Mass Media Message are understandable		
<i>n</i> = 81		
Yes	79	97.5
No	2	2.5
Total	81	100.0

Above table highlights that among 88 women, 81 (92.0%) confirmed that mass media broadcast messages in their preferable language while 7 (8.0%) said no.

Among the women, 79 (97.5%) said that mass media messages are understandable for them while only 2 (2.5%) women said no.

Table – 8

**Frequency distribution of women according to possibility
to watch FP program on TV while sitting with family**

$n = 88$

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	32	36.4
No	56	63.6
Total	88	100.0

Among 88 women, only 32 (36.4%) said they can watch family planning programs on television while sitting with family but majority 56 (63.6%) said no.

Table – 9

**Frequency distribution of women according to family
planning service availed in past**

n = 88

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Availed family planning service in past		
Yes	77	87.5
No	11	12.5
Total	88	100.0
Consulted hospital	<i>n</i> = 77	
Yes	42	54.5
No	35	45.5
Total	77	100.0
Public health center	<i>n</i> = 77	
Yes	32	41.6
No	45	58.4
Total	77	100.0
Consulted doctor	<i>n</i> = 77	
Yes	18	23.4
No	59	76.6
Total	77	100.0

Table-9 elucidates that among 88 women, 77 (87.5%) availed family planning services in the past while 11 (12.5%) women did not avail.

Among women who availed family planning service, 42 (54.5%) consulted hospitals, 32 (41.6%) public health centers and 18 (23.4%) consulted doctors.

Table – 10

**Frequency distribution of women according to personnel
visited homes for family planning**

n = 88

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Family planning personnel visited home		
Yes	23	26.1
No	65	73.9
Total	88	100.0
Who visited	<i>n</i> = 23	
LHW	23	100.0
Other	0	0.0
Total	23	100.0

It is depicted from above table that among 88 women, minority 23(26.1%) stated that family planning personnel visited their homes while 65 (73.9%) women denied this fact.

All 23 (26.1%) women who were visited by family planning personnel said LHW visited them.

Table – 11

**Frequency distribution of women according to consultation
with healthcare provider (HCP)**

n = 86

	Yes	No
HCP used simple language	85 (98.8%)	1 (1.2%)
HCP used simple preferred language	85 (98.8%)	1 (1.2%)
HCP asked medical history	42 (48.8%)	44 (51.2%)
Did physical examination	12 (13.9%)	74 (86.1%)
Told about side effects	72 (83.7%)	14 (16.3%)
Involved spouse in discussion	7 (8.1%)	79 (91.9%)
Answered your concerns	71 (82.6%)	15 (17.4%)
Satisfaction with HCP	67 (77.9%)	19 (22.1%)

Above table describes that among women, 85 (98.8%) said during conversation HCP used simple language, 85 (98.8%) said HCP used simple preferred language, 42 (48.8%) said HCP asked medical history, 12 (13.9%) women were physically examined, 72 (83.7%) women were told about family planning side effects, 7 (8.1%) involved spouse in discussion, 71 (82.6%) answered their concerns and 67 (77.9%) women were satisfied with health care providers.

Figure – 2

Frequency Distribution of Women according to material used by healthcare provider

n = 86

Figure-2 demonstrates that among women, 23 (26.7%) said health officer used booklet for family planning, 4 (4.7%) said contraceptive material and 2(2.3%) said other material.

Table – 13

**Frequency distribution of women according to visit any
center for family planning**

n = 86

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Published material at FP health care center		
Yes	39	45.3
No	47	54.7
Total	86	100.0
Published material in preferred language		
	<i>n</i> = 39	
Yes	39	100.0
No	0	0.0
Total	39	100.0
Difficulty in consultation with HCP		
Yes	12	13.9
No	74	86.1
Total	86	100.0
HCP counseling		
Understood well	26	30.2
Understood	56	65.1
Not understood clearly	4	4.7
Total	86	100.0

Table-13 exhibits that among 88 women, 39 (45.3%) used published material at FP health care center while 47 (54.7%) did not use.

Among women who used published material at FP health care center, 39 (100.0%) said it was in preferred language and 12 (13.9%) women felt difficulty in consultation with HCP.

Result shows that 26 (30.2%) women understood well the HCP counseling, 56 (65.1%) understood and 4 (4.7%) women did not understand clearly the HCP counseling.

Table – 14

**Frequency distribution of women according to difficulty in
communication with healthcare provider**

$n = 86$

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Difficulty in communication with HCP		
Yes	35	40.7
No	51	59.3
Total	86	100.0
Felt shy while querying $n = 35$		
Yes	12	34.3
No	23	65.7
Total	35	100.0
All contraceptive methods not informed $n = 35$		
Yes	15	42.9
No	20	57.1
Total	35	100.0
Time not given properly $n = 35$		
Yes	1	2.9
No	34	97.1
Total	35	100.0
HCP did not satisfied $n = 35$		
Yes	11	31.4
No	24	68.6
Total	35	100.0

Table-14 portrays that among 88 women, 35 (40.7%) had difficulty in communication with health care providers while 51 (59.3%) women had no such difficulty.

Among women who had difficulty in communication with health care providers, 12 (34.35) felt shy while querying, 15 (42.9%) were not informed about contraceptive methods, only 1 (2.9%) women was not given time properly and 11 (31.4%) women were not satisfied with health care providers.

Figure-3

Frequency distribution of women according to degree of Understanding FP Message

n= 86

Figure-3 demonstrates that among women, 26 (30.2%) said they Understand health care personal message very well, 56 (65.10%) said they Understood the message, while 4(4.7%) said that they did not understand the FP message clearly.

Table – 15

Frequency distribution of women according to suggestion

n = 88

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Suggestion		
Yes	80	90.9
Not Responded	8	9.1
Total	88	100.0
Schedule family planning programme on TV	<i>n</i> = 80	
Yes	50	62.5
Not Responded	30	37.5
Total	80	100.0
Educate retrain yearly and monitor LHW	<i>n</i> = 80	
Yes	64	80.0
Not Responded	16	20.0
Total	80	100.0
Publish family planning methods magazine	<i>n</i> = 80	
Yes	18	22.5
Not Responded	62	77.5
Total	80	100.0

Establish free camps offering medicine and treatment	<i>n</i> = 80	
Yes	32	40.0
Not Responded	48	60.0
Total	80	100.0
Introduce mobile phone based information service	<i>n</i> = 80	
Yes	13	16.2
Not Responded	67	83.8
Total	80	100.0
To reveal information about side effects	<i>n</i> = 80	
Yes	49	61.3
Not Responded	31	38.7
Total	80	100.0

Table-15 states that out of 88 women, majority 80 (90.9%) provided suggestions and only 8 (9.1%) women did not provide any suggestion.

Among the women who provided suggestions, 50 (62.5%) said that family planning programs should be broadcasted on regular basis on television, 64(80.0%) said LHWs should be yearly retrained and monitored, 18 (22.5%) said family planning methods should be published in magazine, 32 (40.0%) said free camps providing medicine and treatment should be established, 13 (16.2%) said mobile phone based information services should be

introduced and 49 (61.3%) said that women should be informed about side effects of family planning methods.

Findings of Focus Group Discussion

FOCUS GROUP DISCUSSION FINDINGS:

FGDs were conducted at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital Lahore. Four FGDs were conducted there were 6-8 members in each FGD, the FGDs questionnaire was drafted in English and then translated into Urdu, FGDs were audio recorded and were conducted by the researcher and supervisor.

1: Knowledge and experience with contraception methods

The participants were asked about what sort of information and encounters they had and how they saw each contraceptive method.

In the beginning of discussion women's general concept about the term "Family planning" was asked. Majority of the participants had idea that family planning is a method utilized to keep space between pregnancies and it is good to limit family size while a few of them had no idea about it. Some participants asserted that it is a best way to keep mother and child healthy and helps in reducing the family expense.

One of the participant of focus group discussion shared her knowledge and said:

"My name is Asma, I have 2½ year old son. I think family planning is a method of spacing to keep difference between children. Lack of planning affects mother and child health."(FGD4)

While some of the participants had little knowledge about its meaning and some of them claimed they have No idea about it, this is how a women explain her views:

“I do not have such knowledge. I think it is method of spacing between pregnancies so that mother could grow up children well. I am married since 25 years, I have one son and two daughters. I never used any method. I have natural gap in between my children.” (FGD4)

During discussion respondents were also asked do they need further information about contraception meaning and its detailed methodology to judge how much information they already have.

Half of them desire to have knowledge regarding complete methods of family planning while half of them did not show interest. It was observed that although women had knowledge about the meaning of contraception but majority of the women were unaware of complete methods regarding contraception. Limited access to information from the communication program seemed to produce misinformation among people and allowed for fewer chances to receive accurate information.

1.1: Experience with Contraception methods

Participants were further asked regarding practice and methods used for family planning. Majority of respondents confirmed that they never used any method of family planning. While few of them used Condoms, Implant, Copper-T and BTL.

The reason for the greater percentage of women not following contraception in FGD group was that; these women were visiting family welfare center to seek counselling services for the first time and they were in determined phase to use family planning.

Among the above mentioned methods of FP which women in FGD group adopted, majority of the women were relying on male contraception and copper-t because they fear from side effects of contraception medicine and these methods had relatively less side effects.

A women in FGD shares her experience:

“I am using implant but suffering from heavy menstrual bleeding; now my husband is telling me to use some other method like natural one.” (FGD1)

Implant was the least common method used by women particularly because of the lack of knowledge and thus many speculations about impact of implants on women’s health.

Difference of opinion was observed among participants about breastfeeding as a natural form of contraception, partially due to their misconception. Some women believed that breastfeeding is effective against pregnancy, while others thought that breastfeeding did not prevent pregnancy at all because they themselves had become pregnant, or heard from other women.

A newly married women who delivered her first child a couple of months ago regarding contraception use said:

“This is my first child and I am breastfeeding my child to prolong birth space.”(FGD4)

2: Perception about Family Planning its Pros and Cons.

When participants were asked about their perceptions regarding Contraception Implementation and its pros and cons. Major proportion of respondents was in favor of family planning.

As per respondents, family planning methods are good to be followed as during pregnancy child derives its energy from mother; therefore mother needs time to recover herself. Furthermore according to women the role of mother is very important in family as she has to look after everything. In low income families mothers are also working to help husband. Like one of the women acknowledges the importance of family planning and states:

“In low income families mother also works, they leave their 2^{1/2} year old child in child day care centers due to job and during this period they conceive again particularly due to lack of family planning knowledge, it is a source of stress and problem as one child can be looked after easily therefore family planning knowledge is important.”(FGD4)

Majority of the women were in favor of family planning which shows there is an unmet need and we need to fulfil this demand.

Participants of the group had different religions, some of the participants were hesitating to answer the queries due to their religious beliefs and therefore were failed to be convinced by health personal.

One of the respondent said:

“I think it is not good to act upon family planning methods. If Allah wants to give you children, Allah will give; by using such methods we go against Allah will and He can do anything with our other children.”(FGD3)

But one of the participant explained contraception in light of her religion and said:

“In Islam it is not mentioned to bear consecutive pregnancies burden, to ignore child better development and to destroy own health, it is not written anywhere in Holy Quran and Sunna; those who call family planning non-Islamic practice actually they don't know what Islam is about.”(FGD2)

Participants believed a variety of health problems were caused by contraceptive medicine use. Almost half of the respondents were not utilizing family planning methods due to side effects, the information, experience and rumors about the side effects influenced those who had never used contraceptives, one of the women in interview said:

“I never used family planning methods, I heard people telling about side effects, I think it is risky to use family planning methods.”(FGD3)

One of the respondents said:

“I have heard that women face problems owing to contraception medicines such as heavy menstrual bleeding therefore we never got satisfied to use it, so far, copper T is concerned it has little side effects. I think we can use it to limit the family size.”(FGD1)

3: Perception about Health Care Providers

The following section will describe in more detail; how attitudes and behaviour towards family planning differ as well as change among women due to a variety of interacting factors such as the communication barriers among women and health personal. In this theme of research respondent were asked about their level of satisfaction with information/services provided by health care providers.

Almost half of respondents were satisfied with information/services provided by health care providers.

One 45 years old lady said:

“I often visit family planning center with my daughter in law and I am satisfied with the knowledge which I was provided.”(FGD4)

Their degree of satisfaction was judged by their behavior change regarding family planning.

More than half of the respondents were not satisfied with the assistance of health care providers, few of the participants claimed that health personal did not revealed detailed information about the side effects to them when starting to use contraceptives, while others lack knowledge about complete

contraception methodology deliverance either orally or through IEC material demonstration.

However, lack of information about side effects seemed to make people distrust the health workers. A women participant from one of the focus groups explains:

“My husband and relatives were not satisfied with the information and its application. However, I used Copper-T method as recommended by my healthcare provider, since then I have severe bleeding and becoming weak, those family planning personnel who placed it are not available, I came here at different hospital for its removal.”(FGD1)

Another respondent was satisfied with health care provider, but she said:

“Now I am not satisfied as my Copper-T is displaced, I don't have knowledge about methods other than Copper-T; health care provider did not provided much knowledge to me.”(FGD1)

In reality It may not be the case; may be health care providers were deliberately avoiding telling them side effects to increase compliance, to explore this point it was further discussed with health care providers in In-depth interviews of the research and triangulation of data was done to reach conclusion.

A few of respondents never took information from health care providers.

One respondents said that:

Neither health care provider (LHW) visited my home nor did I visit any family planning welfare center. I don't watch television frequently therefore I do not have knowledge about all family planning procedures and their side effects.”(FGD4)

In such case where popular methods are not availed different population segments should be addressed about the message in accordance to their utilization of different channels of communication, Community events may be of use in such cases.

Majority of the participants had no idea of contraceptive IEC material they had deficient knowledge, one respondent said:

“I have not been educated about detailed methodology of contraception, I never saw any health personnel using IEC material to educate couples.”(FGD4)

4: Modes of Communication for Family Planning Information

One key objective of this theme was to identify people’s familiarity with family planning communication strategies and products.

Respondents were asked that which type of communication channel is easily available for them to get Family planning information.

A significant majority of respondent confirmed that they visit family planning welfare center and hospital for family planning consultation but they also revealed the fact that whenever they visit family welfare center they are not provided with detailed information with the use of IEC material. They further indicated that they are rarely visited by health personnel at home.

A respondent said:

“As all sources of information are not available to everyone, therefore, I think National Programme of family planning is required because when I was living at Sabzazar, Lahore at my mother’s home, LHV used to visit on regular basis but at Gulshan-e-Ravi I am living since three years but no LHV/LHW ever visited my home, it means that they are not working everywhere properly, I never saw any health care provider using IEC material to educate, family planning health center personnel explain orally, therefore rather than introducing newer programmes or investing huge amount on television commercials government should manage national programme of family planning.”(FGD4)

Almost half of the respondents said that television is a source of information regarding family planning and some of them had no source of information regarding family planning because they are confined to home and they rarely go out. Among participants one women said:

“I have no idea because I have no television and I do not visit any hospital.”(FGD2)

Some respondents claimed that relatives were their source of information.

5: Perception about Mass Media Communication.

In this theme of research women were asked about their opinion regarding family planning information telecast on television and its social acceptance keeping in view religious and cultural norms, half of the respondents said they can watch family planning programs on television with their family, As when husband and wife together watch family planning information on television they begin to think about it and consult health care provider in this context. While other considered these programs beneficial for those ladies

who are confined to their homes, like a women satisfied with family planning telecast shared her views and said:

“My mother in law is 70+, she does not go outside home, family planning personnel also never visits, she is not in the process of bearing child but if she watch these family planning program she can guide me and my husband according to that and with her own experience as well.”(FGD4)

One of the respondent said:

“Morning shows are the best platform to convince and guide couples regarding family planning methods.”(FGD4)

Another said:

“Only Signs and Symbols regarding family planning are enough we don't get embarrassed to watch that with family for further consultation we can go to clinic.”(FGD3)

Here it is worth mentioning about the important role of implicit language in communicating sensitive issues.

Some respondents believed that when people watch family planning ads on television, they consult health care provider therefore these messages should be communicated on media which are socially helpful.

Virtually half of the respondents claimed they don't watch family planning programs with family particularly due to joint family system where younger and elder are watching these messages together due to religious and cultural values.

The messages communicated may be appropriate for the younger age group but in our society younger age group lives jointly with older in contrast with western society where such messages may be appropriate.

Participants believed, these commercials affect children thinking.

It was explained by a respondent in such a way:

“Family planning ads should be socially banned as children ask different questions regarding contraception. Currently media is showing a condom add in which a small boy is asking his father at the medical store that “is condom a candy”? And I need this condom candy” This kind of information is not safe for our younger generation.”(FGD2)

Half of the women can't watch family message with their family on television due to their religious and cultural reasons needs further exploration; what are the messages that can't be watched and how these can be tailored according to our customs and religious values. It is important to adopt television messages according to culture and religion.

Here we can see the importance of intermediary communication if media design program in way to initiate dialogue within family it can help the clients.

6: Preference of Communication Channel for family planning

Participants in this theme were asked that what is the best way to communicate about family planning with people?

Majority claimed that doctor is the best source of communication regarding family planning methods as doctor has complete knowledge and can deal with the complications and side effects of contraception medicines, one of the participant said:

“As we take medicine from doctor therefore we should consult her for family planning information as well.”(FGD1)

Half of the respondents viewed that family welfare center and lady health workers visits should be made to promote communication regarding family planning as women are much comfortable if they are counselled privately at home. One of the respondents said:

“Along with medicine and information about family planning, lady health worker should give monthly magazine containing information regarding detail of family planning methods.”(FGD4)

This opinion was further supported by another participant and she said:

“Postpartum period is the best time to educate women, after delivery doctor should include family planning pamphlet in every discharge card of patient to impart family planning health education.”(FGD4)

According to another respondent:

“At Services Hospital Lahore, after delivery health staff asks the will of couple about family planning and do follow up regarding same. This system should be followed everywhere.”(FGD4)

Television, newspaper and internet were suggested by some respondents as sources of communication.

From discussion it was observed that participants much satisfied where doctors and lady health workers educated them through proper channels regarding contraception use and its side effects and showed less interest towards electronic media and mobile as a mode of communication.

Findings of In-Depth Interview with Healthcare Providers at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital

Health care provider's opinion about communication channels for family planning is discussed under seven themes, these health personal were working in different health care centers under SGRH, questionnaire was filled by the researcher while interviewing with the health care providers, communication language was Urdu all interviews were then translated into English. To accommodate tight schedules and time limitations, all of the interviews were conducted once in their offices, which was a choice of the interviewees. Each interview lasted from 15 minutes, participants' body language, expressions and the general atmosphere was also observed.

Theme No. 1: Type of family planning client

Question: What type of clients, you deal with more often?

- A. First visit without any information and knowledge.
- B. First visit with prior information and knowledge.
- C. Using any method with complications and want to change the method.
- D. Satisfied clients for follow up.

Mostly the health care providers agreed that they deal with all four types of clients such as those with first visit without any information and knowledge;

those having prior information and knowledge, clients with family planning method complications and those who are satisfied.

But mostly are the ones with first visit and little knowledge, those having complications and the ones who are satisfied.

In-depth Interview with Senior Doctor at SGRH 55 Years.

“Here we deal with all these four types of clients but mostly are the ones with first visit and little knowledge, those having complications and the ones who are satisfied.”

Theme No. 2: Family planning communication channel

Question: What communication channels are currently being used to convey family planning message?

Existing modes of Communication for family planning communication as reported by health care providers include mass media, doctors, family welfare workers; family welfare counselor, family welfare assistant; IEC material, male and female motivators.

Doctor at SGRH aged 45 years said:

“Here at SGRH at family welfare center we do person to person motivation and counseling. There are separate units for male and female motivation. At departmental level conference and seminars are conducted in which religious scholars are engaged. Hospital population welfare department has appointed male and female welfare assistant who visit door to door and counsel people about family planning.

Theme No. 3: Client satisfaction with FP communication channels

Question: Does mass media messages about family planning issues are sufficient to overcome the concerns of clients?

Health providers acknowledged that mass media and family welfare department play considerable role in overcoming the concerns of clients.

Limitation of family planning information via mass media communication.

Lack of schedule for family planning program on television, shortage of field workers and their limited knowledge could be a barrier in family planning communication.

Theatre Nurse 59 years old said:

“Television alone cannot solve misconceptions and problems of people; family welfare assistants can remove misconceptions of people if properly trained”.

Theme No. 4: Health personal satisfaction with FP Communication channels

Question: Are you satisfied with the existing communication channel?

A close ended question was asked with the health care providers about their satisfaction with the family planning communication channels , all (10) health care providers were satisfied with methodology and information content of communication channels.

Theme No. 5: Improvement of FP communication channel

Question: What are the deficiencies in family planning communication channels and how they can be improved?

Family planning personnel suggested and pointed out the major issues namely training of field workers, shortage of staff at family welfare center, need of grant for post-operative poor patients, free medical camps which are mandatory measures for improvement in communication. In rural areas women lack complete knowledge about family planning due to lack of door to door family welfare workers.

Senior Doctor at SGRH said:

“Earlier before 2011 government offered grant to postoperative poor patients like those undergone BTL, hysterectomy etc. Now grant is not given to the patients, government should make flexible policies regarding this.”

In-depth Interview with Family Welfare Worker 32 years

“Government should increase the number of family planning staff at each family welfare center, train and monitor their performance furthermore field camps should be organized to offer free medicine and family planning education to people.”

Theme No. 6i: Preference of FP communication channel

Question: What is the best communication channel?

- A. To reach family planning clients?
- B. To motivate and satisfy them?

Health care providers were asked regarding preferred communication channel to reach family planning clients. Most of the participants agreed that door to door family health worker field staff is the most convenient method,

however, group discussion facility at neighborhood and television also helps women.

In-depth Interview 4 with Family Welfare Assistant 36 years

“If there are gatherings at town level involving doctors, counselors, religious scholars, lady health workers, lady health visitors and local natives of town, then people could be educated about family planning methodology likewise if medical treatment is provided in comfortable manner then they will definitely learn how to keep space in between children and improve their health”.

Theme No. 6ii: Motivation of family planning client

Respondents were asked that how they can motivate a family planning client? As could be expected they viewed that mass media, health care centers, counsel client from every possible sector ranging from door step till hospital, but mostly clients are satisfied initially later when they face side effects of medicine they become unsatisfied. During interviews it was observed that all health care providers acknowledge that contraception medicines have side effects, women want to follow contraception and there is no medicine without side effects therefore they have no alternative.

Family Welfare Worker at SGRH 32 years old said:

“If there is a client who comes to you for family planning suffering from PID and Cancer; you can neither give her hormones or nor advise Copper-T and if her husband is non-compliant with condom use, which method should we suggest; how do we satisfy her”.

According to another Family Welfare Worker working at SGRH

“If a woman comes to you with heavy bleeding due to contraception use or if a woman on her first visit already knows about the side effects of contraception medicine and she is afraid of using any contraceptive method

along with noncompliance of husband regarding contraception. How should I satisfy and motivate her. If newer methods with less side effects are invented we don't have to counsel the client, it's a matter of medicine side effects not the lack of motivation."

Interview 6 with Operation Assistant Family Welfare Department

"One satisfied client bring another ripple effect, therefore best way to satisfy client is to satisfy each and every client."

Theme No. 7: Health care provider training

Question: Do you think for this purpose there should be capacity building of health care providers for the improvement of their communication skills, e.g. refresher courses.

During last theme health care providers were asked about the need for any training or refresher course, mostly participants oversee the fact that there should be special course for LHV, LHW, FWW, FWC and FWA. Field workers are the main tools for motivation of family planning clients, therefore special training sessions involving FWA male and female need to be conducted once a year. Discussion showed that no refresher courses are introduced by the government.

This is how a theatre nurse share her views.

Theatre Nurse 59 years old having 29 years work experience said:

"I am working since 29 years, I perform all types of surgeries related to family planning, I remember that during 1999 I was trained about surgical techniques by NGO such as sterilization i.e. washing, gowning, draping since then no refresher training was given to us".

Discussion

Implementation of Family Planning Programme in Pakistan remained very challenging due to number of factors including historical, political strife and cultural restrictions on women constraining their empowerment. In most of the countries key barriers for adoption of family planning methods is the lack of information about the locations where family planning services are available and lack of knowledge about the use of family planning methods and the trusted sources for information. Communication enable societies to follow novel ideas to adopt healthy behavior. Communication regarding family planning and reproductive behavior is a challenging job. In most of the countries key barriers for adoption of family planning methods is the lack of information about the locations where family planning services are available, lack of knowledge about the use of family planning methods and the trusted sources for information.

Several campaigns have been launched for the promotion of family planning. Bearing in mind its importance, present study was undertaken regarding assessment of health communication channels for family planning among women of reproductive age at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital Lahore. In this study 88 women were included to obtain adequate results 24 respondents participated in FGDs and 10 Health care providers were in-depth interviewed.

While discussing the socio demographic characteristics it was assessed that majority of the women (65.9%) were 26-35 years old while 26.1% were up to 25 years and only 8.0% women were more than 35 years old. Virtually the similar scenario was showed by a study carried out by Mubarik and associates (2016) who reported that majority of the women (80.0%) were 26-35 years old while 9.2% were up to 25 years and 10.8% women were more than 35 years old.^[38]

Discussing education status of women it was found, 9.1% women were illiterate and 61.4% studied up to matric and 29.5% women were above matric. The results of our study are comparable with the study done by Odhiambo (2015) which showed closely related findings i.e. 11.4% women were illiterate and majority (78.4%) studied up to matric and 10.2% women were above matric.^[19]

During study, duration of marriage of women was also assessed. Study disclosed that almost one-fifth of the women had duration less than 5 years while significant majority had more than 5 years. Among these women, 34.1% had upto 2 children and 46.6% had 3-4 children while 19.3% had more than 4 children. A study undertaken by Oumarou (2014) also showed similar findings 29.7% women had upto 2 children and 49.1% had 3-4 while 21.2% had more than 4 children.^[39]

When frequency distribution of women according to number of children was assessed it was found that women having 1-2 children were 34.1% while the one with 3-4 children was 46.6% it means that women with 1-2 children did not practice family planning therefore percentage of women with 3-4 children grew up and reached to 46.6%. It seems that this group of women is not targeted by family planning communication programme to stop producing more children.

Use of contraceptive is associated with child gender, the people who have no male child or desire more male children do not use contraceptive methods. It is worthwhile to mention that 80.7% women after having 1-2 male children started practicing contraception and came for counselling therefore the percentage of women with 3-4 and above 4 male children was only 14.8%. It shows that families adopt contraceptive methods only when they have desired number of male children. A study undertaken by Oumarou (2014) also showed the similar results that 29.7% women had up to 2 children and 49.1% had 3-4 while 21.2% had more than 4 children.^[39] The study shows a cultural preference of the society for male children which is against the notion of gender equality for that need to be addressed, by the communication strategy of family planning.

Current Contraception prevalence rate of Pakistan is 35.5%.^[2] However in our study we have found that 79.5% of women were using contraception. Among 79.5% women in our study, 42.9% were relying on Condom use, followed by natural methods (27.1%), tablets (24.3%), implant (22.9%), injections (17.1%), tubal ligation (14.3%), Copper-T (11.4%). It shows that women in survey have been using different methods of contraception.

The Percentage of women using contraception in our study is greater because study was conducted at hospital among women who were from urban background, mostly educated and showed health seeking behavior. Study undertaken by Odhiambo (2015) is consistent with our study findings in which he stated that the women who were living in urban setting had greater percentage of contraception use, as compared to the ones who were living in rural areas.^[19]

During FGDs women were asked regarding their experience about contraceptive methods. It was found that most of the respondents confirmed that they never used any method of family planning. Here analysis doesn't correspond with our findings of quantitative survey. The reason for the greater percentage of women not following contraception in FGD group was that; these women were visiting family welfare center to seek counselling services for the first time and they were in determined phase to use family planning.

Some of them were using condoms, implant, copper-T and BTL. Out of above mentioned choices majority of the women were relying on condom and copper-T because they were afraid of side effects of other contraceptive methods. Implant was the least common method used by women due to lack of knowledge and many speculations about impact of implants on women's health.

Result of FGDs and quantitative analysis show similarity regarding women dependence on contraceptive methods having less side effects like natural methods and male condom use, whereas; the percentage of implant use is low in both the results.

Perception about side effects was quite similar between health care providers and clients of our study, and it is the most important barrier in contraception use.

There is need to held medical assistance programs to educate women regarding contraceptive methods and to rectify misconceptions regarding side effects and the information about the health care centres where complications can be treated.

When the knowledge about family planning was assessed, 98.9% women had knowledge about FP but only 79.5% were practicing the family planning methods there is a gap of 19.4% women who had knowledge but were not practicing FP methods. Here the question arises that why these women are

not practicing contraception despite of having knowledge; it may be because they are not motivated or if they are motivated they may not have access; or if they are motivated and have access they may not be following due to side effects. Here in our case it was due to lack of motivation and the fear of side effects which hindered them to follow family planning which is discussed in further part of study. This point was explored by literature review qualitative study of Rehema (2013) in which he stated that percentage of women using contraceptive was (94%) and among them (49.0%) were using injections followed by contraceptive pill (31.0%), natural methods (6.0%), condom (6.0%), IUCD (3.0%), women sterilization (3.0%) and implants (2.0%) Here the use of Implant is also low i.e. only 2% women are using implant. Rehema OB further stated that contraception users were not satisfied with the methods they continue to change methods or completely withdrawn from contraception, with great awareness regarding FP methods, there existed a broad gap between the knowledge and FP methods acceptance and it was due to the side effects of medicine. [7]

To acquire knowledge regarding family planning media plays a significant role among women because majority of women spent their time in watching television and other media. Study found that large numbers of women (94.3%) had media ownership and among these television was the most common media (95.2%), followed by newspaper (26.5%) and radio

(24.1%). Also in FGDs half of the women acknowledge television to be an important source of information.

Our Study further disclosed that 98.9% women had knowledge about family planning. Among these women, 74.7% got knowledge from television programs, 66.7% from LHV/LHW, 37.9% from doctor, 8.1% from newspapers and 5.7% from radio programs. Radio is assessed to be the least important source of knowledge probably because of urban study setting where most of the people have ownership of television.

In a study carried out by Hassan and Baten (2005) regarding role of mass media in promotion of family planning in Bangladesh showed that 39.0% respondents had radio, followed by television (18.0%) and newspaper (7.1%).^[18] From different studies we have seen that priority of media channel varies among different countries and different regions of same country as source of information.

When preferred communication channel among women were evaluated, study divulged that 64.8% preferred doctor, followed by LHV/LHW (50.0%), television (45.5%), mobile phone (11.4%), relatives (8.0%) and newspaper (6.8%). While majority of FDGs respondents preferred to visit family planning welfare center. During discussion, majority viewed that doctor is a better source of knowledge regarding family planning methods as doctor has complete knowledge and can deal with the complications and side effects of contraception medicines. The study reveals that target audience

view doctors as a trustable source of information, knowledge and communication. However the quantitative survey shows that only 37.9% of women indicated doctors as source of information, therefore there is a need for improvement and the government should instruct the doctors to communicate the message of family planning whenever they have the opportunity to do so.

While conducting In-depth interview a Doctor aged 45 years working at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital told that, at SGRH family welfare center they do person to person motivation and counseling. There are separate units for male and women motivation. At departmental level conference and seminars are conducted in which religious scholars are engaged. Hospital population welfare department has appointed male and women welfare assistant who visit door to door and counsel people about family planning.

From the discussion it was observed that mass media despite of being an important source of information and easily available to majority of people is not the preferred channel of communication rather women show much interest towards doctor and lady health workers support the fact that human mind readily accepts interpersonal communication message.

The findings of the study carried out by Alege and teammates (2016) also highlighted the greater impact of health personal regarding contraception

use. Majority (60.4%) women preferred health care providers, followed by media (51.3%) and relatives (17.0%).^[45] The percentage of media also remains low i.e. 51.3% in the study mentioned as compared to health care providers.

The reason of television not being preferred communication channel in our study seems to be that Pakistan is a Muslim country where people follow their cultural values and it is not possible for most of the people to watch family planning programs on television while sitting with families. The results of our study also showed that majority of the women acknowledged that it not possible for them to watch such programs while sitting with family despite of the fact that television is important source of contraception information.

Quantitative study highlighted that 63.5% women cannot watch FP program with family. In this association half of the FGD participants responded that they don't watch family planning programs with family particularly due to joint family system where younger and elder are watching these messages together, due to religious and cultural values.

The messages communicated may be appropriate for the younger age group but in our society younger age group lives jointly with older in contrast with western society where such messages may be appropriate.

Participants viewed that if media displays implicit message rather than explicit message like Signs and symbols of family planning and further consultation at clinic, they will not be embarrassed to watch FP program at television. We can say using explicit language is a barrier created by family planning programme itself. If 63.6% women cannot watch FP program and they cannot discuss with their partners hence in turn affecting spousal communication. We have also found in the study that 91.9% women stated their spouse was not involved with them in family planning discussion by the health personal, thus neglecting spousal communication.

Study conducted in India acknowledges the role of spousal communication and found that spousal communication has significant results in contraception uptake by the people. [21].

Likewise in In-depth interviews health care providers acknowledged that mass media and family welfare department play considerable role in overcoming the concerns of clients, but mass media being an important source of family planning knowledge delivers information with certain limitations. Lack of schedule for family planning program on television, shortage of field workers and their limited knowledge could be a barrier in family planning communication. In In-depth interviews, participants viewed that television alone cannot solve misconceptions and problems of people; because television is one way and passive mode of transfer of information

and knowledge. Health care providers believed that if family welfare assistants are properly trained and educated so that they can address the concerns of the clients; only then clients will be satisfied.

Half of the FGDs participants said that they can watch family planning programs on television with their family, as when husband and wife together watch family planning information on television, they begin to think about it and then consult health care provider in this context to seek assistance. While other considered these programs beneficial for those ladies who are confined to their homes. Respondents viewed that morning shows are the best platform to convince and guide couples regarding family planning methods. Some respondents believed that when people watch family planning ads on television, they consult health care provider therefore these messages should be communicated on media which are socially helpful.

In our study only 11.4 % women showed interest towards mobile phone as a preferred channel of communication regarding FP, less results in favor of mobile phone were due to its limited access for female. Similarly the percentage of relatives was low due to their inadequate knowledge and negative attitude regarding family planning adoption.

It was found during study that majority of women indicated that media used preferable language and among them only 8% said that messages are not understandable. Our study was conducted at urban city where every person understand Urdu language, mass media of Pakistan also uses Urdu to be the mode of communication regarding FP communication, therefore 92% said media uses preferable language. If similar study is conducted at rural area where people don't understand Urdu and communicate in local language we may find different results. The study done by Bonareri (2012) briefed that educated youth understood the message as compared to the uneducated youth where 62.0% respondents said that messages are not understandable, as it was not communicated in their local language.^[40]

Study showed significant results that 87.5% women availed family planning services in the past. Almost comparable results were provided by Parveen and colleagues (2017) who asserted that 77.8% women availed family planning services in the past.^[41] Among these women who availed FP services, majority consulted the hospitals, followed by public health centers, doctors and relatives. A similar study performed by Azmat and partners (2015) demonstrated that majority of the respondents consulted government hospitals, followed by lady health workers, relatives, TBA/mobile services camp, clinics, doctor, LHVs and pharmacy etc.^[42]

There are several misconceptions; therefore, to boost the utilization of family planning methods, health care personnel door to door visits are most important. It is appalling to note that home visits by family planning workers were only 26.1% and all of them were lady health workers.

Likewise significant majority of FGDs respondent confirmed that they visited family planning welfare center and hospital for family planning consultation, where Information was not properly provided in health care centers, IEC material was not used to explain contraception usage. They further indicated that health personal rarely visit their homes.

No satisfactory results were also offered by a study carried out by Sultan and collaborators (2002) who also stated that only 16.0% home were visited by family planning workers. [44]

It is believed that sometimes language is also a barrier that curbs the use of family planning methods but study did not shows such problems because 98.8% women explained that simple and understandable language is used by health care providers. The findings of our study are comparable with the study done by Oumarou (2014) who also confirmed that HCP language was understandable for 100.0% respondent. [39]

Role of family planning material is most important to convince the women if properly utilized by health care providers. It is important to oversee in our study that majority of the women in quantitative analysis were explained

about contraception methodology by HCPs without the use of IEC material, this point is also raised by half of the FGDs participants.

More than half of the respondents were not satisfied with the assistance of health care providers regarding deliverance of the side effects of medicine used for contraception, some of the participants claimed that Information about side effects is not provided by the health care workers when starting to use contraceptives, while others lack knowledge about complete contraception methodology deliverance either orally or through IEC material demonstration.

Study also revealed that almost half of FGDs were satisfied with information/services provided by health care providers.

Furthermore, 59.3% women had no difficulty in communication with HCP. When women were asked regarding their satisfaction of consultation with HCP. In which language, history taking, physical examination and other response of HCP was assessed. Two notable variables in this section were, 86.1% women said that they were not physically examined by the HCP before contraception medicine prescription and only 48.8% were asked about their detailed medical history. But still 77.9% women were satisfied while consulting them. Here the Important role of detailed medical history and physical examination during consultation can only be acknowledged by doctors. Study done by Shah and fellows (2008) showed similar findings

that 60.0% women were satisfied with consultation of health care providers. In this study researcher has not assessed different variables regarding consultation to weigh the degree of client satisfaction. [44]

About (90.9%) women provided suggestions regarding family planning. Among these women, majority said LHWs should be yearly retrained and monitored, followed by FP programs should be broadcasted on regular basis on television, women should be informed about side effects, free camps providing medicine and treatment should be established, family FP methods should be published in magazine and mobile phone based information services should be introduced.

Health care providers in In-depth Interview suggested and pointed out the major issues namely training of field workers, shortage of staff at family welfare center, need of grant for post-operative poor patients, free medical camps which are mandatory measures for improvement in communication. In rural areas women lack complete knowledge about family planning due to lack of door to door family welfare workers.

In In-depth findings participants viewed that earlier government offered grant to postoperative poor patients like those undergone BTL, hysterectomy etc. Now grant is not given to the patients, government should make flexible policies regarding this. Furthermore, government should

increase the number of family planning staff at each family welfare center, train and monitor their performance furthermore field camps should be organized to offer free medicine and family planning education to the population.

Strength and Limitations

- Several measures were taken to ensure the validity of study. Like triangulating with data sources and methods helped us to get more detailed and clear picture of communication channels regarding contraception.
- Different methods of data collection like quantitative, focus group discussion and in-depth interviews helped us to map out and understand fully the dynamics and complexity of human behavior.
- The language of communication was fully understood by the researcher and participants.
- Our study has certain limitations like it was a hospital based study therefore due to tight schedule and time limitations there was difficulty in interacting with women and health care providers and duration of discussion was short.
- As data collection time was one month therefore the sample size was kept small and study was done only on female health care providers and female participant's; response of male health care providers and participants was not taken, therefore there is need of further research in the same field.

Conclusion

The study concluded that family planning program of Pakistan is using different channels of communication which includes mass media, community events, interpersonal communication and digital media.

Study revealed television as one of the most effective channel of communication, however interpersonal communication was a favored mode of communication with greater outcomes and impacts.

Communication campaigns of the family planning program lack situational sensitivity and is failing to respond to the needs of targeted audience. There is lack of information and knowledge about the side effects of contraceptive methods in the population under study because of the capacity issues of health care providers.

Young generation is using mobile technology and social media in greater numbers but that aspect of communication is ignored by the family planning program. Cultural and traditional barriers are still hindering family planning but these issues are not sufficiently addressed by communication strategies.

Recommendations

- Study was conducted at one hospital of Lahore involving only female health care providers and participants, further research by increasing sample size and improving study design based on health workers of government /private sector, NGO staff, male and female participants and religious leaders is important in this context.
- Such study is important to be conducted in rural areas of Pakistan specially Baluchistan to find out the causes of relatively low CPR as compare to other provinces.
- From the research it was found that mostly the women were not satisfied with health care providers due to their inadequate knowledge, failure to convey complete information regarding side effects and deliverance of information without IEC material use, these points can be kept in mind for capacity building of health care provider.
- Family planning health personal should coordinate and arrange with health care facility in the vicinity for patients with FP complications, or separate contraception side effects managing units should be established.
- Refresher for Health Care providers are yearly recommended.

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Annex-1

Questionnaire

Date _____ Serial no: _____

Quantitative Analysis

1. IDENTIFICATION.

1. Name of Respondent: _____

2. Husband Name : _____

3. Age : _____

4. Address : _____

5. Education of Respondent

a. None b. Arabic c. primary d. Higher Education.

6. Married Since.

a. Less than 5 years b. 5-10 years c. 11-15 years d. 16-20 years

e. More than 20 years.

7. Total Number of Children. _____

Boys _____ Girls _____.

8. Have you ever used any contraceptive method?

Yes _____ No _____

8a. If Yes then which method? _____

II KNOWLEDGE AND PERCEPTIONS ABOUT FAMILY PLANNING CHANNELS.

9 .Do you have following at home?

- a. Radio
- b. Television
- c. Newspaper

10. Have you heard about family planning?

Yes_____ No_____

10a. If yes then from which of the following sources you have heard?

- a) Radio programme
- b) Television Spots/Programme.
- c) Newspaper Article
- d) Booklet or Leaflets
- e) Doctor
- f) LHV/LHW
- g) Relatives
- h) Other Specify _____

10b From the list above which source you prefer most regarding family planning? _____

10c If the selected source is mass media then the message delivered to you from

above source are in your preferred language?

Yes___ No_____

10d. Do you understand them?

Yes___ No_____

11. Can you watch Family Planning messages on television with your family?

Yes___ No_____

III COMMUNICATION SKILLS AND METHODOLOGY OF HEALTH CARE PROVIDERS REGARDING FAMILY PLANNING.

12 Have you availed family planning service in past?

Yes_____ No_____

13 If yes then Where do you go for family planning purpose?

a.Hospitalb.Public Health Centre c.GP e.Other_____

14 Have you ever been visited by health personal regarding family
planning at home.

Yes_____ No_____

14a If yes then who _____

15. During Consultation with any family planning health personnel
did the service provider?

a) Use words, you understood well. Yes_____No_____

b) Use your preferred language Yes_____No_____

c) Took your detail medical History Yes_____No_____

d) Did physical examination Yes_____No_____

e) Discussed contraception side effects Yes_____No_____

f) Involved your Spouse in Discussion Yes_____No_____

g) Acknowledge and Respond to your concerns.Yes_____No_____

16. Were you satisfied by the service provided by Health care provider?

Yes_____No_____

17. Did Service Provider use following materials

a) Leaflets Yes_____No_____

b) Contraceptive Samples Yes_____No_____

c) Other_____

18. When you visit Health Care facility for contraception do you?

a) See any family planning information available in printed material?

Yes_____ No_____

b) Find family planning Literature in your preferred language?

Yes_____ No_____

c) Face difficulty in communicating with Health personal?

Yes_____ No_____

d). Do you understand what health personal tells you?

I. Understood well

II. Understood

III. Not Understood Clearly.

19. What is difficulty in communicating with your Health care provider?

V. SUGGESTIONS

20. Any suggestion for improvement regarding communication strategies for family planning.

Thank you very much for your time.

Date _____ Serial no: _____

**B; QUESTIONNAIRE FOR FOCUS GROUP DISCUSSION
(FGD)**

No of Group Interviewed _____	Date: ____/____/ 2017	
Participant names : _____ : _____ : _____ : _____ : _____ : _____ : _____	Time discussion started: _____	Time ended: _____
Participant summary:	Total Number of women _____	
Name(s) of Facilitator(s): _____ _____: _____ _____		

1. What do you know about family planning?

1 a. Do you have experience with contraception?

1 b. If No then attempt question number 2.

1 c. If Yes: Is it about natural contraception or modern contraception?
(explaining both terms).

2. What are your views about Family planning?

Is it good? Why it is good?

2a. If bad, then why?

2b. From where you got this information?

3. Are you satisfied with Information you got about family planning?

3a Do you want further information about any other method?

4. What communication channels are currently available to you for
communicating about family planning?

5. Family planning Campaign run on media, is it socially acceptable?

6a. What are its consequences?

7. What would be the most effective method of this information
Conveyance to you?

Date _____ Serial no: _____

QUESTIONNAIRE REGARDING
INDEPTH INTERVIEW FOR HEALTH CARE PROVIDERS

1. What type of clients, you deal with more often?
A. First visit without any information and knowledge.
B. First visit with prior information and knowledge.
C. Using any method with complications and want to change the method.
D. Satisfied clients for follow up.

2. What communication channels are currently being used for this purpose?

3. Does mass media messages about family planning issues are sufficient to overcome the concerns of clients?

4. Are you satisfied with the existing communication channels?

YES

NO

5. What are their deficiencies how they can be improved?

6. What is the best communication channel?

A. To reach family planning clients

B. To motivate and satisfy them?

-
7. Do you think for this purpose there should be capacity building of health care Providers for improvement of their communication Skills, e.g. training, refreshers, special courses etc?
